

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MOTIVATION AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE STUDENTS' STUDY PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, students' motivation during the educational process, its importance and psychological characteristics are described

Introduction.

Fundamental improvement of the education system, determination of the target directions of training of highly educated specialists, especially the continuous improvement of the professional qualifications and knowledge level of pedagogues are among the most urgent issues. we must pay attention. Education is a complex process aimed at imparting knowledge, skills, qualifications to a student at a certain level and level, as well as developing the mental activity of a person. Education is a complex process aimed at imparting knowledge, skills, qualifications to a student at a certain level and level, as well as developing the mental activity of a person. Education has a two-way character and is carried out as a result of the cooperative activities of the teacher (gives education) and students (receives education). Personal values connect the inner world of a person with the life of society and individual social groups. Any social group - from an individual family to the whole of humanity - is characterized by a focus on certain common values: ideal ideas about what is good, what is desirable, what is right, which summarizes the shared life experience of all members of the group. The transformation of social value into personal value is possible only when a person, together with a group, participates in the practical realization of this common value, when he feels it as his own. Then, a personal value emerges and takes root in the structure of a person - an ideal idea of something that determines the direction of life and serves as a source of meaning.

We can help students develop learning motivation through various methods, psychological research, and motivation. In this regard, the role of methods is incomparable. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process.

According to the currently studied sources of knowledge, the methods are divided into 5 groups and include a number of methods:

1. Practical testing, experimental method:
experimenting, practicing;

participation in training, work, production.

2. Demonstration method:

observation, practice by students.

3. Verbal method:

explain, bring to mind;

to tell a story;

exchange of ideas;

conducting a conversation;

guide, give instructions;

lecture;

discussion, argument

4. Working with the book:

study, study,

quick review;

quote and work on it, write a statement;

writing an abstract, creating a synopsis.

5. Video method:

computer exercise, test solving;

control;

work on the Internet;

preparation of educational films

In short, in order to realize the motivation of education, to master the methods of self-education, it is necessary to set and implement many intermediate goals in the educational system. Through the methods, students acquire specific concepts and skills, they try to use time effectively and work based on accurate scientific knowledge. The use of modern methods of teaching leads to high efficiency in the transition process. Students always need psychological support and help for their learning and development. Through such psychological support, we can monitor the positive change and quality level of students' actions and activities to achieve a predetermined goal.

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